

Which review signals drive sales of high-involvement durable goods? Evidence from Toyota RAV4 in the U.S.

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Abstract

Online reviews are an important information source in high-involvement durable-goods markets, yet their incremental explanatory power at the individual vehicle-model level remains unclear. Focusing on the Toyota RAV4, the best-selling car in the U.S. in 2025, this study constructs a 19-year monthly dataset combining vehicle sales, online reviews, Google Trends, macroeconomic indicators, and major market shocks. Grounded in the Heuristic–Systematic Model (HSM), the study compares multiple review signals using monthly time-series regressions that account for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. The results show that, once macroeconomic conditions, search volume, and calendar effects are rigorously controlled, online review signals provide limited additional explanatory power. Among the measures examined, a sentiment signal based on a simple aggregation of the latest 25 reviews shows the most stable positive association with next-month sales in the preferred specification. By contrast, adding recency or helpfulness weights does not consistently improve model performance. Vehicle recommendation rate and several attribute-level rating measures occasionally yield comparable model fit, but their coefficients are not robust across specifications. Overall, the findings suggest that, in high-involvement durable-goods markets, online reviews function as supplementary rather than dominant indicators of demand. More broadly, the study contributes to the online review literature by introducing a behaviorally grounded measurement approach that better reflects the limited set of recently visible reviews consumers are likely to process before purchase.

Keywords — Electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM); Online reviews; High-involvement durable goods; Vehicle sales; Time-series analysis; Google Trends; Sentiment analysis; Heuristic–systematic processing

Paper type – Research Paper

1. Introduction

Overview

Electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) refers broadly to information exchange generated across digital channels, including online review platforms and social media. Retailers can use e-WOM to identify customer voices and to explain demand and sales (You et al., 2015). Among the various forms of e-WOM, this study focuses on information posted on online review platforms. Online reviews provide both structured indicators, such as ratings, purchase recommendations, and helpful votes, and unstructured textual comments. Because such information accumulates on the same platform over a long period, online reviews are particularly suitable for examining how e-WOM is associated with monthly sales over time (Li et al., 2020).

A substantial body of empirical research has shown that traditional online review indicators, such as volume, valence, and variance, are significantly associated with demand and sales across a wide range of product categories, from low-involvement, high-frequency consumer goods to high-involvement, low-frequency products such as automobiles (Floyd et al., 2014; You et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2022). Online reviews therefore represent a meaningful potential explanatory variable for demand. They also have strategic value because, unlike many conventional indicators such as macroeconomic conditions, they can be monitored and, to some extent, managed or responded to by firms.

Research gaps

The existing literature has two main gaps. First, relatively few studies have systematically examined the long-run association between online reviews and sales at the level of monthly sales for an individual vehicle model in the United States, one of the world's major automobile markets. Automobiles are a representative high-involvement product category, and consumers are likely to examine reviews more carefully before purchase. Nevertheless, prior studies in the automotive context have generally focused on sales at the brand or segment level (Singh et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). However, because firms' product and marketing decisions are implemented at the level of individual models and monthly sales performance, this gap in the unit of analysis is also important from a managerial perspective.

Second, prior studies have not sufficiently reflected how consumers actually process review information. For example, there has been limited evidence on the range of reviews consumers are likely to consider before making a purchase decision, the extent to which they attend to qualitative cues such as recency or helpfulness, and whether summary indicators such as ratings or richer textual information are more useful in explaining market outcomes (Rosario et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Ding et al., 2025). In other words, although it is relatively well established that online reviews are related to sales, it remains insufficiently understood which review signals are more closely associated with monthly sales fluctuations for an individual vehicle model.

Research objectives and methodology

To address these gaps, this study empirically examines

how online reviews are associated with sales at the individual vehicle-model level and the extent to which consumers' review information processing can be indirectly captured. The focal product, the Toyota RAV4, ranked first in U.S. sales in 2024 and is also one of the world's best-selling SUVs (Lyon, 2025; JATO Dynamics, 2025). The study period covers 2007 to 2025. It draws on a long-run monthly dataset that combines review data accumulated on a leading U.S. online automobile platform visited by tens of millions of potential consumers each month with vehicle sales, Google Trends, macroeconomic variables, and major market shocks.

By integrating online reviews, Google Trends, and macroeconomic indicators, this study constructs a 19-year monthly time-series dataset to reflect real market conditions as closely as possible. It also incorporates information-processing theories, particularly the Heuristic–Systematic Model (HSM), into the empirical model design in order to examine consumers' review use indirectly (Chaiken, 1980; Eagly and Chaiken, 1993; Chen and Chaiken, 1999; Tan et al., 2021). Estimation is based on OLS with heteroskedasticity- and autocorrelation-consistent (HAC) standard errors to account for the possibility of heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation in monthly time-series data (Newey and West, 1987).

Contributions

This study makes two main contributions. First, it extends the literature by examining the association between online reviews and monthly sales at the level of an individual vehicle model, thereby complementing prior studies that have largely focused on sales at the segment or brand level. Second, it explores how consumers of high-involvement durable goods process online review information at the individual model level.

More specifically, this study examines (i) how the range of reviews that consumers are likely to encounter before purchase is associated with sales, (ii) whether qualitative properties of online reviews, such as recency and helpfulness, provide additional explanatory power, (iii) whether heuristic cues (e.g., vehicle ratings and recommendation share) or systematic processing signals (e.g., review text) are more closely associated with sales, and (iv) which product-related review signals are more closely linked to sales. In doing so, the study provides evidence on which review indicators managers and distributors should prioritize when monitoring demand.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature and develops the hypotheses. Section 3 presents the data and methodology. Section 4 reports the empirical results. Section 5 discusses the findings, implications, and limitations.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. e-WOM and Sales Performance

2.1.1. General evidence across product categories and meta-analyses

In the online review literature, traditional e-WOM indicators such as review volume, average rating valence, and rating variance have commonly been used as core signals for explaining demand and sales. Meta-analyses and large-scale empirical studies report that these indicators are generally significantly associated with performance across a wide range of product categories and platforms (Floyd et al., 2014; Rosario et al., 2016). Rosario et al. (2016), for example, synthesize 96 studies and document an overall positive relationship between e-WOM and performance, while also showing that review volume and valence exhibit relatively consistent associations with performance.

These findings suggest that online reviews can influence purchase outcomes by increasing consumer awareness and shaping persuasion during the pre-purchase information search process. However, prior studies have often relied on simple monthly or quarterly averages when constructing review sentiment measures (El-Said, 2020), while only limited attention has been paid to qualitative properties such as review recency and helpfulness (Wang et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2022). As a result, the existing literature does not sufficiently reflect the actual order and range in which consumers read reviews, or the qualitative cues to which they may pay greater attention. Accordingly, this study develops review measures that more closely approximate actual consumer information processing and compares the relative explanatory power of alternative review signals.

2.1.2. Automobile sales and e-WOM

Online reviews also function as an important information signal in high-involvement durable-goods markets such as automobiles. Before purchase, consumers explore performance, quality, maintenance costs, and safety information through multiple sources, including test drives and online reviews. In this context, other consumers' usage experiences can serve as a key cue for reducing perceived financial risk. A growing body of prior research provides evidence that online reviews are significantly associated with vehicle sales and suggests that authentic user experiences may serve as especially strong risk-reduction signals for high-priced and high-risk products (Rosario et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023).

However, prior studies have often remained at the level of brand- or segment-level aggregates (Singh et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023), and relatively few studies have systematically examined the explanatory power of online review signals using long-run monthly sales data for a single vehicle model. Accordingly, this study analyzes the association between online reviews and sales at the individual model level by focusing on a top-selling SUV in the U.S. market.

In addition, prior studies that explain or predict fluctuations in automobile sales using online reviews have typically included review indicators together with macroeconomic indicators, consumer sentiment, and online search volume, all of which capture demand and

supply conditions (Zhang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2023). Likewise, this study systematically controls for macroeconomic indicators, search volume, calendar effects, and policy and industry shocks in order to reflect actual market conditions as closely as possible.

2.2. Heuristic–Systematic Model (HSM)

The Heuristic–Systematic Model (HSM) posits that decision makers seek a balance between cognitive effort and judgmental accuracy. According to the sufficiency principle of HSM, individuals continue searching for information until they reach a subjectively acceptable confidence threshold, after which they stop further search (Chaiken, 1980; Eagly and Chaiken, 1993; Chen and Chaiken, 1999; Winter, 2020). This implies that consumers may rely only on a limited amount of information before reaching a purchase decision.

From this perspective, consumers may form judgments based on only a subset of the most recently visible reviews on an online review platform. By contrast, prior online review studies have typically constructed monthly or quarterly sentiment measures by aggregating all reviews posted during a given period, regardless of the number of reviews involved (Ding et al., 2025; Zhang and Wu, 2023). It is therefore necessary to test separately whether review signals based on the set of recently visible reviews that consumers are more likely to process provide greater explanatory power than conventional period-level aggregates.

Accordingly, based on the sufficiency principle and the reverse-chronological user interface of the focal review platform, this study examines whether the aggregated sentiment of a small set of the most recent reviews that consumers are likely to encounter at a given point in time explains next-month vehicle sales better than the sentiment aggregated from all reviews posted during a given month. Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H1a. Sentiment extracted from monthly aggregated reviews is positively associated with next-month vehicle sales.

H1b. Sentiment extracted from the latest *N* reviews is positively associated with next-month vehicle sales.

H1c. Sentiment extracted from the latest *N* reviews may explain next-month vehicle sales better than sentiment extracted from monthly aggregated reviews.

HSM further suggests that when individuals are motivated to minimize cognitive effort, they are more likely to rely on heuristic cues that enable low-effort judgments, such as average ratings and recommendation shares. By contrast, when more accurate judgment is required, they may rely on systematic processing signals, such as narrative review text, which require greater cognitive effort to process (Chaiken, 1980; Winter, 2020; Maslowska et al., 2020).

In the focal online review platform, summary indicators such as vehicle ratings and recommendation shares are prominently displayed, increasing the visibility of

heuristic cues. At the same time, because automobiles are high-involvement products, consumers also have strong incentives to read review text carefully in order to make accurate judgments. Accordingly, this study compares the associations of these two types of review signals with monthly vehicle sales. Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H2a. Heuristic cues (average vehicle rating) are positively associated with next-month vehicle sales.

H2b. Heuristic cues (vehicle recommendation share) are positively associated with next-month vehicle sales.

H3. Systematic processing signals (sentiment extracted from vehicle review text) may explain next-month vehicle sales better than heuristic cues (average vehicle rating and recommendation share).

In other words, H3 compares the relative explanatory power of text-based signals, as conceptualized in H1, with that of summary indicator-based signals, as conceptualized in H2a and H2b.

2.3. Multiattribute Utility Theory

According to Multiattribute Utility Theory, a consumer's overall utility can be expressed as a weighted sum of utilities derived from individual attributes, and each attribute carries a different level of importance (Keeney and Raiffa, 1993; Dyer, 2016). This suggests that, because automobiles comprise multiple attributes such as Interior, Value, and Reliability, consumers may not assign the same level of importance to every attribute when making a purchase decision.

For example, consumers facing stronger budget constraints may place greater weight on Value, while treating attributes such as Interior as relatively secondary. Against this background, this study examines whether the extent to which attribute-specific ratings in automobile reviews explain monthly vehicle sales differs across attributes. Because attribute-level ratings in online reviews can serve as heuristic cues in consumers' purchase decisions, the following hypothesis is proposed.

H4. The extent to which attribute-specific heuristic cues (e.g., the average ratings of Interior, Reliability, and other attributes) explain monthly vehicle sales differs across attributes.

2.4. Limited Attention in Online Review Processing

From the perspective of limited attention, consumer attention is a scarce cognitive resource. In environments characterized by information overload, individuals may not process all review information to the same extent and may instead rely on a small subset of reviews that are prominently displayed by the platform (Jabr and Rahman, 2022).

On the focal platform, as on many other online review platforms, reviews are sorted in reverse chronological order. From a limited-attention perspective, consumers may allocate greater attention to a small number of the most recent reviews displayed at the top of the page.

Empirical evidence also suggests that individual reviews shown near the top of a page can exert a stronger influence on purchase probability (Vana and Lambrecht, 2021).

This suggests that recent reviews may have a relatively stronger influence on actual purchase decisions. Accordingly, this study compares the explanatory power of specifications that apply recency weights to review signals with that of simple unweighted specifications. Based on this reasoning, the following directional hypothesis is proposed.

H5. Incorporating recency weights into review signals may increase their explanatory power for next-month vehicle sales.

2.5. Signaling Theory and Helpfulness Votes

According to Signaling Theory, individuals tend to refer to others' judgments rather than rely solely on their own when seeking to reduce risk under conditions of information asymmetry. Reviews marked as helpful by many users may therefore be interpreted as information that has been socially validated by other consumers (Connelly et al., 2011). Lee and Choeh (2020), using box office data, show that online reviews with higher helpfulness votes better explain and predict movie sales.

Accordingly, reviews that are evaluated as helpful by many consumers may exert a greater influence on decision-making than reviews that are not. This suggests that review signals weighted by helpfulness votes may explain vehicle sales more precisely. Based on this reasoning, the following hypothesis is proposed.

H6. Incorporating helpfulness weights into review signals may increase their explanatory power for next-month vehicle sales.

The conceptual framework summarizing the above hypotheses is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

3. Data and Methodology

This study examines the extent to which online review signals and related information cues that consumers actually encounter in the U.S. market explain monthly sales fluctuations for an individual vehicle model. To do so, it constructs a monthly time-series dataset that combines U.S. Toyota RAV4 sales, online reviews, search

volume indices, major macroeconomic and industry indicators, product life-cycle factors, and calendar effects, and estimates linear regression-based time-series models. The data sources, variable definitions, and estimation procedures are described sequentially in Sections 3.1–3.6.

3.1. Data Collection and Variable Construction

3.1.1. General principles

This study constructed raw monthly time-series data for the U.S. market from May 2006 to January 2025. However, the descriptive statistics and regression analyses are reported based on the common analysis sample, in which all essential variables are jointly observed. The following principles were applied during data collection.

First, not seasonally adjusted (NSA) series were used whenever possible. This is because the dependent variable, monthly vehicle sales, and key independent variables, such as the Google Trends index, are provided in NSA form. However, for Real Personal Income Excluding Transfers (W875RX1), the original source, the U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA), publishes only a seasonally adjusted (SA) series, and this variable was therefore included in SA form as an exception (U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2025). This unavoidable combination of SA and NSA series is also generally accepted in prior studies that estimate monthly automobile demand by combining vehicle sales with macroeconomic indicators (Xu et al., 2023).

Second, the variables used in this study were collected from publicly accessible open sources. This was intended to improve data accessibility and enable third parties to reproduce the same procedure.

3.1.2. Monthly vehicle sales

Because manufacturer-disclosed information on monthly Toyota RAV4 sales from 2006 to 2025 is limited, monthly RAV4 sales data were collected from GoodCarBadCar (GCBC), a website that compiles vehicle sales figures (GoodCarBadCar, 2025). The resulting series was then checked for potential anomalies against monthly, quarterly, and annual sales results disclosed by Toyota Motor North America, to the extent that such information was available.

3.1.3. Online review

Consumer review data were collected from a U.S. online automobile review platform. Figure 2 shows an example of the upper section of the platform interface, where users are first exposed to the cumulative average overall rating, attribute-specific average ratings, and the vehicle recommendation share (X% of drivers recommend this car). In this study, these summary indicators are defined as review heuristic cues.

2025 Toyota RAV4 consumer reviews

\$29,800–\$31,200 MSRP range

5.0 ★★★★★ (3 reviews)
100% of drivers recommend this car

Rating breakdown (out of 5):

Comfort	5.0
Interior	4.7
Performance	4.5
Value	4.7
Exterior	4.7
Reliability	4.7

[Write a review](#)
[Explore the 2025 Toyota RAV4](#)
[Shop the 2025 Toyota RAV4](#)

Figure 2. Example of review heuristic cues

Figure 3 shows an example of the lower section of the platform interface, where consumers can scroll down to read review text after viewing the summary information presented at the top of the page. In this study, such narrative information is defined as review text signals.

4.0 ★★★★★ ☆

Great car overall but have have had problems with

March 30, 2025
By John from Queens, new york
Owns this car

Great car overall but have have had problems with radio/screen. Needed to go back to dealer to reboot. As a current owner of now 2 Toyotas only disappointment was service.

Rating breakdown (out of 5):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Purchased a New car ● Used for Commuting ● Does recommend this car
Comfort	4.0
Interior	4.0
Performance	4.0
Value	3.0
Exterior	5.0
Reliability	4.0

0 people out of 0 found this review helpful. Did you?

[Hide full review](#) ^

Figure 3. Example of review text signals

In this study, only reviews of the gasoline powertrain were used. The gasoline powertrain was sold continuously throughout the observation period, whereas hybrid and other powertrains were not sold in more than half of the months, making stable estimation in a monthly time-series model difficult.

Given the sales share of the gasoline-powered Toyota RAV4, reviews of gasoline vehicles may be regarded as having a reasonable degree of representativeness. Although the sales share of other powertrains, including hybrids, has steadily increased, gasoline models still accounted for more than half of total sales in 2023 and remained the best-selling powertrain in 2024 (Toyota Motor North America, 2025).

In addition, when analyzing monthly sales, this study uses only reviews of the current RAV4 generation on sale in each month. The Toyota RAV4 has undergone periodic full model changes, including the introduction of the

fourth generation in 2012 and the fifth generation in 2018, and each generation change involves substantial differences in design and functionality (Toyota Motor Sales, U.S.A., Inc., 2012; Toyota Motor Sales, U.S.A., Inc., 2018). Prior research also suggests that intergenerational differences, including design changes, can have a significant effect on sales performance (Talke et al., 2017). Taking these considerations into account, this study treats RAV4 vehicles within the same generation as the same product, whereas RAV4 vehicles belonging to different generations are treated as different products.

3.1.4. Macroeconomic variables

Macroeconomic indicators such as income, prices, interest rate spreads, and the inventory-to-sales ratio are known to affect automobile sales through demand, supply, and financial channels (Sa-ngasoongsong et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2020; Kim, 2023). Accordingly, this study includes major macroeconomic indicators, including real income, as control variables. The detailed list of variables and their definitions are presented in Table 1.

Macroeconomic indicators expressed in U.S. dollars were collected in inflation-adjusted form from authoritative sources, including FRED (Federal Reserve Economic Data) provided by the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis. This was intended to ensure that nominal monetary indicators were incorporated as real values whenever possible.

3.1.5. Google Trends

Search volume indicators such as Google Trends can indirectly capture consumers' active consideration and may serve as leading signals of sales (Carrière-Swallow and Labbé, 2013; Zhang et al., 2020). This study collected the monthly Google Trends search index for the term "Toyota RAV4." The geographic scope was limited to the United States, and the search options were set to "Search term" and "All categories" in order to capture the overall level of interest in the Toyota RAV4 in the U.S. market.

3.1.6. Product life-cycle variables

To control for sharp sales changes around new model launches, this study includes release dummies corresponding to the generation changes of the gasoline powertrain in January 2013 (fourth generation) and December 2018 (fifth generation) (Toyota Motor Sales, U.S.A., Inc., 2012; Toyota Motor Sales, U.S.A., Inc., 2018).

Prior literature suggests that the effects of new product launches tend to be concentrated in a short period of approximately one to three months immediately after launch (Pauwels et al., 2004; Beuk et al., 2014). This study considers both the finding of Pauwels et al. (2004) that market responses to new product information are concentrated in the first two months after launch and the practical reality that actual launch dates may vary within a month, from the beginning to the end of the month. Accordingly, the first three months following a generation change are defined as the initial period in which new-model effects are most likely to appear.

Although the Toyota RAV4 is offered with multiple powertrains in addition to gasoline, gasoline was used as the reference point because it was sold continuously throughout the observation period and accounted for the largest sales share (see Section 3.1.3). Because the timing of generation changes differs across powertrains, including additional dummy variables for the launch dates of non-gasoline powertrains would substantially increase the number of parameters to be estimated relative to the sample size, thereby increasing the risk of overfitting and reducing interpretability. By contrast, prior research on model selection recommends favoring more parsimonious models over unnecessarily complex models with too many parameters, particularly when predictive performance and interpretability are both important (Ding et al., 2018).

3.1.7. Exceptional shock variables

This study includes the following dummy variables to capture irregular and intermittent macro shocks.

First, to reflect U.S. recession periods, this study uses the NBER-based recession indicator provided by FRED. Specifically, a dummy value of 1 was assigned to December 2007 to June 2009 (the global financial crisis period) and to February 2020 to April 2020 (the COVID-19 recession period), both of which were classified as recession periods by the NBER (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, n.d.).

Second, the Cash-for-Clunkers program was a subsidy policy that generated a temporary spike in vehicle sales. Accordingly, a dummy value of 1 was assigned to July and August 2009, the policy implementation period (U.S. Department of Energy, 2009).

Third, the 2023 UAW strike disrupted production at major Toyota competitors, including General Motors, Ford, and Stellantis. Accordingly, a dummy value of 1 was assigned to September and October 2023, the months in which the strike occurred (Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System, 2024).

3.1.8. Selling days and calendar controls

Monthly vehicle sales are strongly affected by seasonality and calendar-related factors. This study therefore includes variables to control for these effects. Seasonality was controlled for by including monthly dummy variables (February to December, with January as the reference month). Calendar effects were controlled for by including monthly selling days as a continuous independent variable.

Because it is difficult to directly observe actual dealership operating days for individual dealers at the national level, this study constructs a proxy for monthly selling days using weekday information. In the United States, Sunday vehicle sales are legally restricted in some states, limiting Sunday dealership operations (WardsAuto, 2017), whereas Saturday operations are widespread (WardsAuto, 2002). Accordingly, this study defines monthly selling days as the total number of calendar days minus the number of Sundays.

Table 1

Definitions and measurement of variables

Variable	Definition	Measurement	Source
Sales (DV)	Monthly sales of Toyota RAV4 in the U.S.	Monthly units sold; level series	Toyota USA; GCBC
Ratings (IV)	overall rating, ratings per attributes	Monthly avg. rating	online review
recommendation rates (IV)	X% of drivers recommend this car	% of "recommend"	online review
Sentiment (latest-N, simple) (IV)	Text-based sentiment without attention weighting	VADER compound score over latest-N reviews	online review
Sentiment (latest-N × rank-decay) (IV)	Attention-weighted sentiment by recency	VADER × rank-decay weight	online review
Sentiment (latest-N × rank-decay × helpfulness) (IV)	Attention-weighted sentiment by recency & helpfulness	VADER × rank-decay × helpfulness	online review
Chicago Fed National Activity Index (CFNAI) ©	Broad business cycle indicator	Index	FRED
Real Personal Income Excl. Transfers (W875RX1) ©	Household real income	Real dollars; SA	FRED
Google Trends "Toyota RAV4" ©	Model-specific search intensity	Google Trends index	Google Trends
Retail Inventories/Sales Ratio: MV & Parts (MRTSIR441USN) ©	Dealer inventory pressure	Ratio	FRED
10Y–3M Term Spread (T10Y3M) ©	Financial conditions, yield curve slope	Percentage points	FRED
Buying Conditions for Vehicles (U-Mich) ©	Auto-specific consumer sentiment	Index	Univ. of Michigan
Motor Vehicle Retail Sales: Light Trucks (LTRUCKNSA) ©	Segment-level demand proxy	Units	FRED
CPI: New Vehicles (CUUR0000SETA01) ©	New vehicle price index	CPI index	FRED
CPI: Motor Fuel (CUUR0000SETB) ©	Operating cost of vehicles	CPI index	FRED
Real Broad Dollar Index (RTWEXBGS) ©	External competitiveness / FX conditions	Index	FRED
Housing Permits (PERMITNSA) ©	Real economy & housing pipeline	Level	FRED
U.S. monthly selling days ©	Number of selling days per month	Days	Author's calculation

Cash-for-Clunkers ©	Temporary scrappage stimulus	Dummy = 1 for 2009.07–2009.08	U.S. DOE; refs
U.S. recessions (NBER) ©	Official recession periods	Dummy = 1 during NBER recession months	NBER; FRED
2023 UAW strike ©	Strike-related supply disruption	Dummy = 1 for 2023.09–2023.10	FEDS Notes; news
New-model release windows ©	RAV4 launch / facelift periods	Dummies for specified launch windows (e.g., 2013.01–03; 2018.12–2019.02)	Toyota releases / press
Month fixed effects (1–12) ©	Monthly seasonality	11 dummies (baseline = January)	Researcher defined

Note. © indicates control variables, DV denotes the dependent variable, and IV denotes independent variables.

3.2. Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics of the main variables used in this study, including the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values. Although the raw data cover the period from May 2006 to January 2025, the descriptive statistics reported in this table are based on the common analysis sample spanning April 2007 to January 2025, for which all variables are available.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
RAV4 sales	25762.83	11313.57	6502	49481
Average rating	4.55	0.39	2	5
Recommendation share	89.00	12.90	0	100
Average text sentiment	0.70	0.07	0.4947444	0.9477
Google Trends index for "Toyota RAV4"	46.22	25.27	15	100
Selling days	26.10	0.82	24	27
Chicago Fed National Activity Index	-0.17	1.51	-18.19	6.31
Buying conditions for vehicles	115.67	30.78	35	152
Retail inventories/sales ratio	2.01	0.38	1.11	3.32
Light truck retail sales	793.12	224.12	340.354	1272.569
CPI: New vehicles	149.74	13.46	132.264	179.75
10Y-3M term spread	1.37	1.32	-1.74	3.69
Real broad dollar index	100.67	10.21	83.9047	122.6375
Housing permits	98.12	32.01	36.3	173

Note. All variables are based on monthly observations. Definitions of the variables and data sources are provided in Table 1.

3.3. Data Preprocessing

3.3.1. Temporal alignment of online review variables

In this study, review text signals were constructed based on the current generation, whereas review heuristic cues were constructed based on the current model year. This distinction reflects the possibility that consumers may encounter and use these two types of signals differently in actual decision-making contexts. First, review text contains specific user experiences and attribute evaluations, making it reasonable to distinguish such information by generation boundaries, where vehicle design and functionality change substantially. When evaluating a currently marketed vehicle, consumers may also browse textual reviews of prior model years, and, particularly when reviews of the current generation are limited, they may refer to reviews of adjacent earlier model years within the same generation. In other words, text reviews are likely to be interpreted more in terms of product characteristics and usage experiences shared within the same generation than in terms of differences across individual model years.

By contrast, review heuristic cues, such as average ratings and recommendation shares, are summary indicators that consumers can instantly observe on the platform screen, and on the focal platform these indicators are presented at the model-year level. Accordingly, it is more appropriate to construct heuristic cues based on the current model year, which corresponds to the unit in which consumers actually encounter the information. In short, whereas text reviews represent relatively flexible information that consumers may browse across multiple model years within the same generation as needed, ratings and recommendation shares are static summary indicators calculated and displayed by the platform for a specific model-year page. Treating them on a model-year basis therefore more closely reflects the actual information environment.

In both cases, the explanatory variables for sales month (t) were constructed using only review information that had been publicly available up to the end of the previous month ($t-1$). This procedure was adopted to prevent a look-ahead problem. This timing assumption is also consistent with industry evidence suggesting that online information search and vehicle purchase activities are concentrated within a relatively short period. According to a Cox Automotive survey of approximately 2,300 U.S. vehicle buyers, the total time spent on information search and purchase activities before buying a vehicle was about 14 hours, of which about 7 hours were spent on online channels (Cox Automotive, 2025).

For control variables other than online reviews, different lags were applied depending on each variable's economic and institutional characteristics and the time required for its effects to be reflected in monthly vehicle sales. The detailed lag structure is described in Section 3.4.

3.3.2. Standardization, missing values, and outlier handling

An examination of the distribution of the dependent variable, monthly Toyota RAV4 sales, based on

descriptive statistics and histograms, showed a skewness of 0.310, indicating no pronounced extreme asymmetry. Accordingly, for ease of interpretation and preservation of the original unit, the dependent variable was retained in levels. By contrast, continuous independent variables other than dummy variables were standardized using z-scores before estimation.

Missing values were handled using interpolation or replacement methods deemed appropriate to the source of the missingness. First, monthly RAV4 sales data collected from GCBC were checked for anomalies against monthly, quarterly, and annual sales results disclosed by Toyota Motor North America. As a result, the June 2022 sales observation, which had been recorded as zero, was replaced with the manufacturer-disclosed value (Toyota Motor North America, 2022; see Section 3.1.2).

In addition, the review data from the focal platform include not only the overall rating but also attribute-specific ratings such as Comfort, Interior, Performance, Value, Exterior, and Reliability, as well as the vehicle recommendation share displayed as “X% of drivers recommend this car” (see Section 3.1.3). Some of these variables were missing in certain months. When a value for a given month was missing, the replacement value was first calculated as the mean based only on review information accumulated up to that point within the same vehicle generation.

If no prior information was available within the same generation, a pre-defined constant consistent with the scale of the corresponding variable was used. In addition, a variable-specific missingness indicator was included in the regression models to capture the possibility that the absence of information itself could affect the outcome.

More specifically, if a value for the same model year was available, that value was used first. Only when no review for the same model year existed by that point, or when the relevant attribute value was missing, was the value replaced with the cumulative historical mean up to the end of the previous month within the same generation. A pre-defined constant was used only when no prior information existed even within the same generation.

3.4. Moving-average windows and lag specification for control variables

Control variables such as macroeconomic indicators and search volume may affect monthly vehicle sales, but the timing and speed of their effects may differ across variables (Wang et al., 2023). Some variables may be reflected relatively quickly, whereas others may affect sales more gradually over several months.

Search and sentiment indicators tend to capture short-term fluctuations in automobile demand relatively quickly, whereas financial and exchange-rate variables tend to be reflected more gradually through prices and purchasing conditions. In addition, the yield curve is widely used as a leading indicator of recessions several quarters ahead, while real activity indicators such as housing permits tend to affect consumer markets more slowly through

production and investment processes. To reflect these differences, this study fixed the moving-average window and lag of each control variable ex ante. The detailed specification for each variable is presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Moving-average windows and lag specification by variable

Variable	Moving Average	Lag
Chicago Fed National Activity Index (CFNAI)	3	1
Real Personal Income (Excl. Transfers) (W875RX1)	3	1
Google Trends	1	1
Buying Conditions for Vehicles Umich (Auto Sector Consumer Confidence)	1	1
Retail Inventories/Sales Ratio: Motor Vehicle and Parts Dealers (MRTSIR441USN)	1	1
Motor Vehicle Retail Sales: Light Weight Trucks (LTRUCKNSA)	1	1
Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: New Vehicles in the U.S. City Average (CUUR0000SETA01)	3	1
Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: Motor Fuel in the U.S. City Average (CUUR0000SETB)	3	1
10-Year Treasury Constant Maturity Minus 3-Month Treasury Constant Maturity (T10Y3M)	3	6
Real Broad Dollar Index (RTWEXBGS)	3	3
New Privately-Owned Housing Units Authorized in Permit-Issuing Places: Total Units (PERMITNSA)	6	6

3.5. Construction of Review-Based Variables

3.5.1. Review heuristic cues and review text signals

As explained in Section 3.1.3, this study classifies review indicators into two categories.

First, review heuristic cues refer to the cumulative average overall rating, cumulative average attribute-specific ratings, and vehicle recommendation share provided by the focal platform. These indicators are summary statistics that consumers can immediately observe at the top of the online review platform and that enable them to form an initial judgment about the vehicle with relatively little cognitive effort. Accordingly, this study defines them as heuristic cues from the perspective of HSM.

Second, review text signals refer to the individual review texts provided by the platform. This information is located in the lower section of the review site and generally requires greater cognitive effort to process than summary ratings. Accordingly, this study defines such information as systematic processing signals from the perspective of HSM.

To quantify review text signals, this study computes sentiment scores. Specifically, the sentiment of each review is measured using the compound score generated by the VADER lexicon-based model. VADER was developed to analyze short, informal, and social-media-like text (Hutto and Gilbert, 2014), and prior empirical studies report that, for this type of data, it performs at least comparably to, and in some cases better than, other widely used lexicon-based sentiment analysis tools (Rustam et al., 2021; Min and Zulkarnain, 2020).

3.5.2. Aggregation of review text signals

This study aggregates review text signals in two ways. (i)

Monthly review aggregation follows the conventional approach used in many prior studies by aggregating all reviews posted within a given month (Ding et al., 2025; Zhang and Wu, 2023). (ii) Latest-N review aggregation assumes that consumers read only a limited number of reviews displayed near the top of the page and is based on the sufficiency principle of HSM and the review-sorting logic of the focal platform, which presents reviews in reverse chronological order. The explanatory power of review text signals aggregated under these two approaches is then compared with respect to monthly vehicle sales. Through this comparison, the study seeks to indirectly infer actual consumer information-processing patterns.

Depending on the review text aggregation approach, two types of review shortage dummies are defined so that situations in which review information is absent or insufficient are reflected in the model. These are defined as follows.

(i) Under monthly review aggregation, a dummy value of 1 is assigned to a month when the number of review texts posted in that month is zero.

(ii) Under the latest-N review aggregation, a dummy value of 1 is assigned to a month when the cumulative number of review texts within the current generation is smaller than the selected N. This is because, in the monthly sales analysis, only reviews of the current generation on sale in that month are used (see Section 3.1.3), and reviews may not yet have accumulated sufficiently in the early stage of a generation transition.

To explore the number of reviews (N) under the latest-N aggregation, the candidate set was defined as $N \in \{1, 3, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30\}$. This set is stratified across small, medium, and large values, thereby allowing consideration of cases in which consumers read only a few reviews as well as cases in which they examine a relatively larger set of reviews. The optimal number of latest reviews (N) was then selected based on the specification that provided the greatest explanatory power for monthly vehicle sales according to the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). When BIC values were identical, the specification with the higher adjusted R^2 was preferred.

3.5.3. Weighting schemes for review text signals

In constructing review text signals, this study applies two types of weights to the sentiment score of each of the latest N reviews: (i) recency and (ii) helpfulness votes. This is intended to reflect the qualitative properties of reviews and to more closely mimic actual consumer information search. The specific weighting procedures are as follows.

(i) Recency

To reflect review recency, this study applies rank-based decay according to the display order of reviews. This approach is based on the review-sorting logic of the focal platform, which presents reviews in reverse chronological order, as well as empirical evidence showing that, in such an environment, individual reviews displayed near the top

of the page exert a strong effect on purchase probability (Vana and Lambrecht, 2021).

Alternative approaches, such as time decay, could also be considered instead of rank-based decay. However, because such approaches do not directly align with the design of this study, which assumes that consumers refer to the latest N reviews, they are excluded from the scope of analysis. The decay formula adopts exponential weighting (Hunter, 1986), which is a standard method with established stability in control and forecasting applications (Yoon and Clarke, 1993). The exponential weighting formula is given in Equation (1).

$$R_r = \exp\{-\lambda(r-1)\},$$

$$r = 1, \dots, N \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\ln 2}{h-1}$$

Where:

- R_r denotes the recency weight assigned to the review displayed at rank r.
- r denotes the display rank sorted by recency, where r = 1 indicates the most recent review.
- N denotes the number of recent reviews included in the analysis.
- λ denotes the decay rate defined based on the half-rank h, such that the weight of the review displayed at rank h is set to one-half of the weight assigned to the most recent review.

The decay rate is defined through the half-rank h. The half-rank is the reference point at which the influence of the h-th review is set to decline to half the influence of the first review in a reverse-chronological review environment. For example, when h = 2, the sentiment score of the second review is weighted at one-half the level of the most recent review. When h = 10, the sentiment score of the tenth review is weighted at one-half the level of the most recent review.

This structure makes it possible to test quantitatively how much weight consumers place on recent reviews. This study defines the candidate set as $h \in \{2, 3, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30\}$ and searches for the optimal value based on the minimization of the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). This candidate set is likewise stratified across small, medium, and large values, thereby allowing broad consideration of cases in which consumers focus on only a small number of reviews as well as cases in which they examine a relatively larger number of reviews.

Figure 4 visualizes how the weights vary across values of h. The x-axis represents the review rank (r), where x = 1 indicates the first, that is, the most recent review. The y-axis represents the recency weight assigned to the review

at rank r . As reviews become older, the assigned weight declines in an exponential form.

Figure 4. Rank-based exponential decay function by half-rank (h)

ii) Helpfulness votes

In this study, helpfulness weights were constructed using the review voting information displayed on the platform (i.e., “x out of y people found this review helpful”). This approach is grounded in signaling theory and prior empirical research suggesting that online reviews with higher helpfulness are more likely to be perceived as relatively credible information and may therefore provide greater explanatory power for sales outcomes (Connelly et al., 2011; Lee and Choeh, 2020).

Review helpfulness was calculated using the platform’s helpful and unhelpful vote counts. Let (pos_r) denote the number of helpful votes and (neg_r) denote the number of unhelpful votes for review (r). Helpfulness was then computed as shown in Equation (2). To avoid extreme values when both helpful and unhelpful votes were zero, additive smoothing was applied using the Jeffreys prior ($\alpha = 1/2$)

$$H_r = \frac{pos_r + \alpha}{pos_r + neg_r + 2\alpha}, \quad \alpha = 0.5 \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

This study uses the helpfulness value defined in Equation (2) as a proxy for review credibility. However, it does not assume that consumers calculate review credibility in actual information processing in exactly the same way as Equation (2). Although prior research has used helpfulness indicators as a qualitative property of reviews (Lee and Choeh, 2020), to the best of our knowledge no prior study has quantified and validated the exact way in which consumers process such information.

In addition, because helpfulness information is based on votes accumulated after a review is posted, it may not perfectly match the set of information actually available to consumers at each sales month. Accordingly, review signals incorporating helpfulness should be interpreted as ex post proxies for the relative usefulness and salience of reviews.

By applying both recency and helpfulness weights, the monthly review text signal is finally calculated as shown in Equation (3). Specifically, the recency weight (R_r) from Equation (1) and the helpfulness value (H_r) from Equation (2) are combined and then normalized so that the combined weights sum to one.

$$\tilde{W}_r^{RH} = \frac{R_r \cdot H_r}{\sum_{j=1}^N R_j \cdot H_j}, \quad r = 1, \dots, N \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

$$S_t^{(N,h,H)} = \sum_{r=1}^N \tilde{W}_r^{RH} \cdot s_r$$

- \tilde{W}_r^{RH} : the final normalized weight for review (r), combining recency and helpfulness
- $S_t^{(N,h,H)}$: the monthly review signal in month (t) incorporating the final normalized weights
- s_r : the text sentiment score of review (r) among the latest (N) reviews observed for month (t)
- R_r : the recency weight of review (r) among the latest (N) reviews observed for month (t) (Equation 1)
- h : the half-rank parameter governing the slope of rank-based decay (Equation 1)
- H_r : the helpfulness weight of review (r) (Equation 2)
- N : the number of latest reviews defined at the beginning of this section

3.6. Model Specification and Estimation

3.6.1. Final regression model

The main objective of this study is to interpret intuitively the extent to which review indicators are associated with monthly vehicle sales. Accordingly, a linear regression model is employed and estimated using ordinary least squares (OLS) in order to quantify the contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable.

Standard errors are computed using the Newey–West heteroskedasticity- and autocorrelation-consistent (HAC) estimator with a Bartlett kernel (Newey and West, 1987). Letting (T) denote the number of observations in each regression, the maximum lag length is set to $L = [4(T/100)^{2/9}]$. This rule is intended to reflect the possible range of residual autocorrelation in monthly time-series data consistently according to sample size, rather than fixing it arbitrarily.

This approach makes it possible to obtain consistent standard errors even when autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity are present in monthly time-series data. By contrast, conventional OLS without HAC remains valid only under the assumption that residuals are independently and identically distributed. In monthly data,

however, residuals are often serially correlated, and their variance may increase during particular periods such as pandemics or recessions. As a result, standard errors may be underestimated, leading to misleading p-values.

The final regression framework of this study can be summarized as in Equation (4). To compare the explanatory power of different review signals, each regression specification includes either a review text signal ($S_{t-1}^{(N,h,H)}$) or a review heuristic cue (C_{t-1}), but not both simultaneously. The specification including review text signals is presented in Equation (4a), whereas the specification including review heuristic cues is presented in Equation (4b).

The dependent variable Y_t is measured as the level of monthly Toyota RAV4 sales, and continuous independent variables are standardized as monthly z-scores (see Section 3.3.2). To prevent look-ahead bias, all review text signals and review heuristic cues are constructed using only information observable up to the end of the previous month (see Section 3.3.1). The definitions and detailed construction procedures of the independent variables are described in Sections 3.1–3.5.

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 S_{t-1}^{(N,h,H)} + \gamma^\top X_{t-L}^{(R)} + \delta^\top D_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4a)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 C_{t-1} + \gamma^\top X_{t-L}^{(R)} + \delta^\top D_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4b)$$

- Y_t : Toyota RAV4 sales in month (t)
- $S_{t-1}^{(N,h,H)}$: the sentiment-based review text signal for the latest (N) reviews of the current-generation gasoline vehicle, incorporating both half-rank- (h) -based recency weights and helpfulness weights
- C_{t-1} : the heuristic cue indicator for the current-generation gasoline vehicle
- $X_{t-L}^{(R)}$: the vector of control variables (e.g., macroeconomic indicators and Google Trends) with variable-specific lags and moving-average

windows applied

- D_t : the vector of dummy variables indicating review shortages, generation changes, calendar controls, and policy shocks
- ε_t : the error term

3.6.2. Estimation procedure

As noted in the preceding sections (see Sections 3.4 and 3.5.2), this study explores multiple specifications involving different review signals (e.g., average ratings and text sentiment scores) and hyperparameters (e.g., the number of reviews incorporated and the recency-weighting parameter). The final specification is selected in two steps. First, candidate models are restricted to those satisfying the multicollinearity criterion of $Max\ VIF \leq 10$ and, at the same time, yielding a HAC-robust p-value below 0.10 for the focal review coefficient. Among these candidates, the specification with the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) is selected. When BIC values are identical, the specification with the higher adjusted R^2 is preferred.

Both BIC and adjusted R^2 deteriorate when unnecessary independent variables are added. They therefore offer the advantages of discouraging overfitting and improving interpretability regarding the contribution of each variable. Although the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is similar to BIC, AIC is designed to minimize expected prediction error and therefore tends to favor more complex models, whereas BIC places relatively greater emphasis on model parsimony. Accordingly, in the present explanatory context, BIC is more appropriate (Schwarz, 1978; Zhang, Yang and Ding, 2023). Statistical inference for the regression coefficients is based on HAC (Newey–West) standard errors that are robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation (Newey and West, 1987).

4. Empirical Results

4.1. Baseline Control Specification

Table 4 presents the baseline control specification of this study. As described in Section 3.4, the moving-average windows and lag structures for the control variables were fixed ex ante based on economic interpretation and prior literature. The baseline control model was estimated while maintaining this control-variable structure, and multicollinearity diagnostics were conducted only for the continuous explanatory variables. The comparison of review signals in Section 4.2 was likewise performed while holding this baseline control structure fixed.

As shown in Table 4, in the baseline control specification, the Google Trends index, light truck retail sales, the real broad dollar index, the motor vehicle and parts inventory-to-sales ratio, and selling days were significantly associated with monthly Toyota RAV4 sales. Specifically, the Google Trends index ($\beta = 6142.1606$, $p < 0.01$) and light truck retail sales ($\beta = 4510.0215$, $p < 0.01$) showed positive associations with sales. The real broad dollar index ($\beta = 2146.6285$, $p < 0.05$), the motor vehicle and parts inventory-to-sales ratio ($\beta = 1838.9761$, $p < 0.05$), and selling days ($\beta = 1251.5474$, $p < 0.05$) also exhibited positive coefficient signs. By contrast, the coefficients of the CFNAI, the vehicle buying conditions index, the new vehicle consumer price index, the interest rate spread, and housing permits were not statistically significant.

Among the exceptional shock and calendar control variables, the 2023 UAW strike dummy ($\beta = 4719.6636$, $p < 0.01$) showed a positive association, whereas the new-model release dummy ($\beta = -4327.2072$, $p < 0.01$) showed a negative association. In addition, all monthly dummies from February to December had significantly positive coefficients relative to January, suggesting clear monthly seasonality. By contrast, the Cash-for-Clunkers dummy and the recession dummy were not statistically significant in the baseline specification.

The explanatory-power decomposition results show that the Google Trends index (22.54%), light truck retail sales (18.77%), and the real broad dollar index (17.51%) made relatively large contributions. The maximum variance inflation factor (max VIF), calculated using only the continuous explanatory variables, was 8.82, satisfying the pre-specified threshold of below 10. Accordingly, the baseline control specification was judged to be suitable for use as the benchmark model for subsequent comparisons of review signals, without indicating a serious multicollinearity problem.

The baseline control specification showed a relatively high adjusted R^2 of 0.8677, and the BIC was 4281.152. In addition, both the HAC-robust Wald test and the conventional OLS F-test supported the overall statistical significance of the model ($p < 0.001$). The maximum variance inflation factor (max VIF), again calculated using only the continuous explanatory variables, was 8.824, satisfying the pre-specified threshold of below 10.

Table 4

Baseline Control Specification

Variable (Series code)	β (HAC se)	p	VIF
Selling days	1251.5474*** (447.7024)	0.01	1.04
Chicago Fed National Activity Index (CFNAI)	58.0537 (457.4780)	0.90	1.40
Google Trends "Toyota RAV4"	6142.1606*** (1219.8348)	0.00	8.82
Buying Conditions for Vehicles (U-Mich)	1421.1647 (1141.9408)	0.21	6.09
Retail Inventories/Sales Ratio: MV & Parts (MRTSIR441USN)	1838.9761** (707.8674)	0.01	2.28
Motor Vehicle Retail Sales: Light Trucks (LTRUCKNSA)	4510.0215*** (953.9885)	0.00	6.00
CPI: New Vehicles (CUUR0000SETA01)	-453.3707 (1150.9384)	0.69	6.37
10Y-3M Term Spread (T10Y3M/T10Y3MM)	621.8682 (714.6215)	0.39	2.71
Real Broad Dollar Index (RTWEXBGS)	2146.6285** (825.4737)	0.01	5.97
New Privately Owned Housing Units Authorized (PERMITNSA)	-178.6704 (647.2855)	0.78	3.77

Note. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Values in parentheses are HAC-robust standard errors (Newey–West). The dependent variable is monthly Toyota RAV4 sales.

Note. The maximum variance inflation factor (max VIF) was calculated using only the continuous explanatory variables. Design-based control variables, such as monthly dummies and policy/event dummies, are reported separately and were not included in assessing whether the threshold was satisfied.

Note. Continuous explanatory variables were standardized using z-scores, whereas dummy variables were not standardized.

Note. The full period of the raw data is May 2006 to January 2025, and the common analysis sample spans April 2007 to January 2025. The baseline control specification includes 214 observations and 26 regression variables including the intercept. The model's BIC is 4281.152, and the adjusted (R^2) is 0.8677. The HAC-robust Wald F statistic is 108.062 ($p < 0.001$), and the conventional OLS F statistic is 56.862 ($p < 0.001$). The maximum VIF based on the continuous explanatory variables is 8.824.

4.2. Comparison of Review Signals: Text Signals, Weighted Text Signals, and Attribute-Specific Heuristic Cues

Table 5 presents the comparison results for candidate review specifications estimated on the same common analysis sample. To prevent the final selection from being driven by specifications in which the coefficient of the focal theoretical variable, the review signal, was effectively absent, this study first restricted the candidate set to admissible models that simultaneously satisfied two criteria: max VIF < 10 based on the continuous explanatory variables and a HAC-robust p-value < 0.10 for the review variable. The final specification was then selected as the model that minimized the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) within this admissible set. When BIC values were identical, the model with the larger adjusted R^2 was preferred. Accordingly, the final specification reported in this section is not simply the model with the lowest BIC among all explored models, but rather the best admissible model among those passing the pre-defined screening rules.

As shown in Table 5, among the text-based specifications, the latest-N specification based on the simple aggregation of the latest 25 reviews was selected as the final specification within the admissible candidate set. The review coefficient in this specification was positive and met a weak level of statistical significance ($\beta = 978.4240$, ($p = 0.09$)). By contrast, the

Monthly specification, which aggregates all reviews posted within a given month, also showed a positive coefficient but was not statistically significant ($\beta = 208.6585$, ($p = 0.64$)), and its model fit was also inferior to that of the latest-N specification. Accordingly, H1a was not supported, H1b received weak support, and H1c can be interpreted as receiving limited support in that the latest-N specification showed a lower BIC and a higher adjusted (R^2) than the Monthly specification.

Specifications that additionally incorporated recency weights and helpfulness weights all retained positive coefficient signs, but they did not show consistently better explanatory power than the simple latest-N aggregation. The latest-N \times recency specification yielded $\beta = 925.9998$ and ($p = 0.11$), failing to meet the significance threshold. Likewise, the latest-N \times recency \times helpfulness specification yielded $\beta = 903.8209$ and ($p = 0.12$), which was also not statistically significant. The latest-N \times helpfulness specification yielded $\beta = 952.0173$ and ($p = 0.09$), meeting a weak significance threshold, but it was not superior to the simple latest-N specification in terms of BIC or adjusted (R^2). Therefore, H5, which predicted that recency weighting would improve explanatory power, was not supported, and H6, which predicted that helpfulness weighting would improve explanatory power, likewise did not receive consistent support.

Among the heuristic-cue specifications, the vehicle recommendation share and some attribute-specific rating specifications showed relatively low BIC values. In particular, the Comfort rating (4284.540), Value rating (4284.760), and vehicle recommendation share (4284.970) all exhibited lower BIC values than the latest-N specification. However, the review coefficients in these specifications were all statistically insignificant ($p = 0.21$)–(0.23). Likewise, the overall rating, Interior rating, Performance rating, Exterior rating, and Reliability rating also showed no significant association. Accordingly, H2a, which predicted a significant positive relationship between the average vehicle rating and next-month sales, and H2b, which predicted a significant positive relationship between the vehicle recommendation share and next-month sales, were not supported.

The evidence for H3, which predicted that text-based signals would explain sales better than heuristic cues, was also limited. The final latest-N specification was the only text-based specification within the admissible candidate set that satisfied a weak significance threshold, yet some heuristic-cue specifications showed lower BIC values. However, because the coefficients of those heuristic cues were not statistically significant, it is difficult to conclude that text-based signals were consistently superior. Therefore, H3 is best interpreted as receiving weak partial support or limited support.

H4, which concerned attribute-specific heuristic cues, also did not receive clear support. Although BIC differences existed across the attribute-specific rating specifications, none of the attribute coefficients was statistically significant, and the differences in explanatory power across attributes did not show a consistent pattern. Accordingly, H4 was interpreted as not supported.

Taken together, the results in Table 5 suggest that online review text signals may have a weak positive association with next-month sales for an individual vehicle model, but that the effect is limited and sensitive to specification choices. In particular, the text sentiment measure based on the simple aggregation of the latest 25 reviews emerged as the most persuasive text-based specification under the final selection rule, but specifications that additionally incorporated recency or helpfulness weighting did not consistently improve upon it. In addition, the vehicle recommendation share and some attribute-specific ratings showed competitive values in terms of model fit, but their coefficients did not achieve statistical significance. The variable-level estimation results, relative contributions, and multicollinearity diagnostics for the final selected model are reported in Appendix Table A1.

Table 5

Comparison of Review Signal Specifications

Review Variable	N	h	BIC / Δ BIC	Adj. R^2 / Δ Adj. R^2	β (HAC se)	P	# regressors (incl. intercept)
Monthly	—	—	4286.262 / 5.110	0.867116 / -0.000549	208.6585 (442.6177)	0.64	28
latest-N	25	—	4286.105 / 4.953	0.869805 / 0.002141	978.4240* (573.8776)	0.09	29
latest-N \times recency	25	30	4286.776 / 5.624	0.869397 / 0.001732	925.9998 (578.9839)	0.11	29
latest-N \times helpfulness	25	—	4286.163 / 5.011	0.869770 / 0.002105	952.0173* (563.9715)	0.09	29
latest-N \times recency \times helpfulness	25	30	4286.809 / 5.658	0.869376 / 0.001711	903.8209 (572.5113)	0.12	29
X% of drivers recommend this car †	—	—	4284.970 / 3.819	0.867916 / 0.000251	780.5793 (615.1191)	0.21	28
Overall rating †	—	—	4286.153 / 5.001	0.867184 / -0.000480	429.9472 (691.7864)	0.53	28
Comfort rating †	—	—	4284.540 / 3.388	0.868181 / 0.000516	784.3932 (647.5138)	0.23	28
Interior rating †	—	—	4286.085 / 4.933	0.867226 / -0.000438	415.4360 (683.9073)	0.54	28
Performance rating †	—	—	4286.160 / 5.008	0.867180 / -0.000485	379.3869 (647.3956)	0.56	28

Value rating [†]	—	—	4284.760 / 3.608	0.868045 / 0.000380	819.8613 (655.0873)	0.21	28
Exterior rating [†]	—	—	4286.403 / 5.251	0.867028 / - 0.000637	220.2071 (738.5330)	0.77	28
Reliability rating [†]	—	—	4285.929 / 4.777	0.867323 / - 0.000342	660.9468 (847.7827)	0.44	28

Note. [†] indicates that, when some monthly values of the heuristic-cue variable were missing, they were replaced with an expanding historical mean calculated from review-level information available up to the end of month (t-1) within the same generation. If no prior information was available within the same generation, a pre-defined constant consistent with the variable scale was used instead (rating = 3.0; vehicle recommendation share = 50.0). In addition, a dummy variable indicating missingness for each variable was included in the regression equation.

Note. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Values in parentheses are HAC-robust standard errors (Newey–West). The dependent variable is monthly Toyota RAV4 sales.

Note. ΔBIC is defined as $BIC_{Final} - BIC_{Robustness}$. Therefore, a larger ΔBIC indicates that the candidate specification has a lower BIC than the baseline control specification.

Note. Within the latest-N family, the specification with the lowest BIC was reported among the admissible candidates that simultaneously satisfied $\max VIF < 10$ and HAC-robust ($p < 0.10$). If no specification within the same family satisfied both criteria, the raw BIC-minimizing specification was reported. When BIC values were identical, the specification with the higher adjusted R^2 was preferred.

4.3. Robustness Checks and Model Diagnostics

4.3.1. Robustness checks

This study examined the robustness of the final selected model in two ways. First, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by adjusting the moving-average windows and lag structures of the control variables, which had been fixed ex ante in the baseline control specification, within a range of ± 1 . Second, to examine whether the exceptional shock during the early stage of the COVID-19 pandemic exerted undue influence on the results, the model was re-estimated after excluding the period from February 2020 to April 2020. All robustness checks involving adjustments to moving-average windows and lags were conducted while holding the same common analysis sample fixed as in the final selected model (April 2007 to January 2025, $N = 214$). Accordingly, these results reflect the effects of specification changes rather than changes in sample composition. By contrast, the COVID-19-excluded specification removed only those three months from the same common analysis sample and therefore contains 211 observations.

The robustness checks focused on the ΔBIC of each alternative specification relative to the final selected model, as well as the sign of the review coefficient and whether its significance level was retained. As reported in Table 6, the review coefficient consistently retained a positive sign across all robustness specifications. Moreover, with the exception of the Window -1 specification, all ΔBIC values were greater than zero, indicating that many alternative specifications showed lower BIC values than the final selected model. Specifically, ($\Delta BIC = 13.93$) for the Lag $+1$ specification, ($\Delta BIC = 84.48$) for the Lag -1 specification, ($\Delta BIC = 19.95$) for the Window $+1$ specification, and ($\Delta BIC = 85.43$) for the COVID-19-excluded specification. Only the Window -1 specification was somewhat less favorable, with ($\Delta BIC = -6.39$). Even in this case, however, the review coefficient remained positive and met a weak significance threshold ($p = 0.064$).

The statistical significance of the review coefficient was also generally preserved. In the final selected model, the review coefficient was ($\beta = 978.4240$) with ($p = 0.0899$). In the Lag $+1$, Lag -1 , Window $+1$, and COVID-19-excluded specifications, the review coefficient was significant at the 5% level in all cases. Accordingly, the positive association between the review text signal and next-month sales observed in the final selected model can be interpreted as being broadly maintained even when the moving-average windows and lag structures of the control variables are slightly adjusted or when the early COVID-19 period is excluded. These robustness results therefore support the view that the direction of the review effect is relatively stable.

Table 6

Robustness Checks

Robustness specification	ΔBIC	Review beta(HAC se)	p-value	Direction consistent?	n_obs
Final	0	978.4240* (573.8776)	0.089876118	Yes	214
Lag +1	13.92755986	1279.4594** (577.4540)	0.027939191	Yes	213
Lag -1	84.47988671	1143.3408** (496.4818)	0.022397829	Yes	214
Window -1	-6.387477912	1098.2370* (588.9338)	0.063794861	Yes	214
Window +1	19.94703283	1269.6895** (577.1593)	0.029060092	Yes	213
Excluding COVID-19 (2020-02 to 2020-04)	85.43260935	1270.8070** (557.0461)	0.023680642	Yes	211

Note. Final refers to the final specification selected in Section 4.2 based on BIC among the admissible candidates satisfying the pre-specified screening rules (max VIF < 10 and review HAC-robust ($p < 0.10$)).

Note. The Lag ± 1 and Window ± 1 robustness specifications were all re-estimated using the same common analysis sample as the final selected model (April 2007 to January 2025, $N = 214$). The COVID-19-excluded specification was estimated after removing only February 2020 to April 2020 from the same common analysis sample and therefore has ($N = 211$).

Note. ΔBIC is defined as $BIC_{Final} - BIC_{Robustness}$. Therefore, $\Delta BIC > 0$ indicates that the robustness specification has a lower BIC than the final selected model.

Note. “Direction consistent?” indicates whether the sign of the review coefficient is the same as that of the final selected model.

Note. Values in parentheses are HAC-robust standard errors (Newey–West). The dependent variable is monthly Toyota RAV4 sales.

4.3.2. Model diagnostics: autocorrelation and multicollinearity

Diagnostic tests for residual autocorrelation and multicollinearity were conducted for the final selected model. As reported in Table 7, the p-value of the Breusch–Godfrey LM test was 1.12×10^{-5} , and the p-value of the Ljung–Box Q(12) test was 4.68×10^{-6} . Both tests therefore rejected the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation, suggesting that some degree of residual autocorrelation remained in the final selected model. By contrast, the maximum variance inflation factor (max VIF) was 9.678, which is below 10, indicating that serious multicollinearity among the continuous explanatory variables is unlikely to be a major concern.

These diagnostic results require careful interpretation. The presence of residual autocorrelation suggests that the error structure of the model may not have been fully captured and that the efficiency of the coefficient estimates may therefore be limited. However, because statistical inference in this study is based on the HAC (Newey–West) covariance matrix, which is robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation, the presence of autocorrelation does not necessarily invalidate inference on the coefficients themselves. In other words, this result is more appropriately understood as a limitation in efficiency rather than as a threat to the validity of coefficient inference. Even so, future research should consider alternative time-series models or additional dynamic corrections that more explicitly account for the residual structure.

In addition, the VIF diagnostics were conducted only for the continuous explanatory variables. Monthly dummies and policy/event dummies were included in the regression as design-based control variables, but they were excluded from the VIF calculation and from the assessment of whether the threshold was satisfied. This treatment is consistent with the model selection rule adopted in this study.

Table 7

Model Diagnostic Results

Breusch-Godfrey LM p-value	Ljung-Box Q(12) p-value	Max VIF
1.12112E-05	4.68002E-06	9.67

Note. The diagnostic results were computed for the final selected model adopted according to the pre-screening and model-selection rules described in Section 4.2.

Note. The criteria for concluding no autocorrelation were Breusch–Godfrey ($p > 0.05$) and Ljung–Box Q(12) ($p > 0.05$), and the criterion for concluding no serious multicollinearity was max VIF < 10.

Note. The maximum variance inflation factor (max VIF) was calculated using only the continuous explanatory variables. Monthly dummies and policy/event dummies were included in the regression equation but excluded from the VIF diagnostics.

5. Discussion

This study explored which online review signals are more closely associated with monthly sales fluctuations for an individual vehicle model in the context of high-involvement durable-goods purchases. Prior research has repeatedly documented an overall positive association between online reviews and sales performance, but the unit of analysis has often remained at the brand or segment level, and the analysis has frequently centered on summary indicators such as review volume and average ratings (Floyd et al., 2014; Rosario et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). By contrast, this study extends the literature by directly linking monthly sales of a single vehicle model in the U.S. market to text-based signals derived from recent reviews, thereby indirectly examining consumers’ online review information processing at a more granular level.

The main findings can be summarized as follows. First, the text sentiment measure based on the simple aggregation of the

latest 25 reviews showed a weak positive association in the final selected model and exhibited relatively better model fit than the specification aggregating all reviews posted within a month. Second, specifications that additionally incorporated recency or helpfulness weights generally retained positive coefficient signs, but they did not consistently improve on the simple latest-N specification. Third, vehicle recommendation share and some attribute-specific ratings showed competitive values in terms of model fit, but their coefficients were generally not statistically significant. Fourth, in the robustness checks, the review coefficient generally retained a positive sign, although the autocorrelation diagnostics also suggested that the final selected model may not fully satisfy an ideal error structure.

These findings do not imply that online reviews have no implications for sales. Rather, they suggest that text-based review signals may still function as supplementary cues of demand even at the level of an individual vehicle model. However, the effect was not strong. In other words, although the general positive relationship reported in the e-WOM literature is not fully contradicted in the present context, the results suggest that the relationship may be much more limited at the level of a single vehicle model's monthly sales in a high-involvement durable-goods market. In this sense, the present study does not merely support prior research; rather, it re-evaluates its scope of applicability using a more demanding unit of analysis.

5.1. Theoretical implications

This study offers several theoretical implications. First, it indirectly infers how automobile buyers process information by drawing on the Heuristic–Systematic Model (HSM) (Chaiken, 1980; Winter, 2020; Maslowska et al., 2020). From the perspective of the sufficiency principle, the findings suggest that, before purchasing a vehicle, consumers may concentrate their information search on a limited number of recent reviews within a given platform. The results also imply that, in the purchase context of high-priced and high-risk products such as automobiles, consumers may consider not only heuristic cues such as vehicle ratings and recommendation shares, but also the more specific information contained in review text. Finally, according to Multiattribute Utility Theory, consumers do not evaluate all attributes equally when assessing high-involvement multiattribute products, and they may respond more sensitively to information related to attributes that matter more to them (Keeney and Raiffa, 1993; Dyer, 2016). This study is meaningful in that it explores this possibility by combining online review data and sales data at the individual vehicle-model level.

Second, from the perspective of limited attention, this study examines whether recently posted reviews may be more closely linked to actual purchase decisions (Jabr and Rahman, 2022; Vana and Lambrecht, 2021). However, the analysis did not provide consistent evidence that sentiment indicators weighted by review order outperformed the simple aggregation measure. Rather, in the final selected specification, only the text-based sentiment measure constructed by simply aggregating the latest 25 reviews showed a weak positive association with next-month sales, whereas specifications that additionally incorporated recency or helpfulness weights did not show consistent improvements in explanatory power. This does not necessarily deny that consumers may prioritize recent reviews. Instead, it suggests that the effect may be captured only in a limited way in monthly data.

Third, from the perspective of signaling theory, this study examined whether review helpfulness can function as a credible quality signal under conditions of information asymmetry (Connelly et al., 2011; Lee and Choeh, 2020). However, in the present analysis, text indicators that incorporated helpfulness weights did not consistently show greater explanatory power. Accordingly, rather than concluding that helpfulness is always a stronger signal, this study suggests that, in high-involvement durable-goods markets, review text content, recency, and product context may jointly matter more than helpfulness alone.

5.2. Managerial implications

This study also offers several managerial implications. First, the analytical framework developed here may be useful in the product-planning stage for identifying which attribute-related consumer evaluation signals warrant closer attention. By examining the relationship between attribute-specific review signals and sales, firms may explore, at the model level, which attributes appear to elicit relatively stronger consumer responses. Although it cannot be concluded that the effect of a particular attribute is consistently significant across all periods and specifications, the framework may still serve as a useful initial diagnostic tool for identifying which attributes are more likely to be linked to demand. For example, if evaluations related to interior quality or reliability repeatedly emerge as promising candidates, firms may use this as one basis for prioritizing limited development resources and cost budgets toward improving interior quality or reliability rather than exterior styling.

Second, the findings provide implications for marketing message design. Once the attributes to which consumers are more likely to respond are identified, those attributes may be emphasized more prominently in marketing communications and retail sales settings. For example, if review signals related to interior quality emerge as relatively important candidates, firms may consider redesigning advertising and promotional messages around themes such as premium interior finishing or perceived quality. Likewise, if reliability-related signals appear important, it may be more appropriate to emphasize warranty coverage and maintenance stability rather than price discounts. However, the present results should be understood as suggesting broad strategic directions; such message strategies should still be validated through additional market experiments or consumer research before implementation.

Third, the findings may inform the design of KPIs for review management. In the present analysis, the simple sentiment measure based on the latest 25 review texts showed a stronger association with next-month sales than cumulative summary indicators such as vehicle ratings or recommendation shares. From a practical perspective, this suggests that firms may need to monitor changes in the emotional tone of recently posted, highly visible reviews more sensitively than they monitor all cumulative review indicators mechanically. Accordingly, it may be important to detect whether negative reviews become concentrated within a short period for a given vehicle model, to identify the causes quickly when such negative tone is detected, and to encourage positive experiences formed at customer touchpoints such as test drives or delivery to translate into actual online reviews.

5.3. Limitations and directions for future research

Despite its meaningful implications, this study has several limitations.

First, it does not fully reproduce consumers' actual information-processing process. By aggregating the latest N reviews and constructing indicators that incorporate recency and helpfulness weights, this study attempts a measurement approach that is closer to consumer behavior than the conventional monthly average aggregation approach. However, these measures remain proxy variables that simulate the consumer information-processing process rather than directly observe which reviews individual consumers actually read and to what extent. In addition, whereas information displayed on online review platforms is updated in real time as reviews are posted, this study quantifies review signals using cumulative information available at the end of each month. This temporal simplification may not fully match the actual timing of exposure. At the same time, prior studies on the relationship between online reviews and sales have also largely relied on monthly or quarterly panel data (Ding et al., 2025; Zhang and Wu, 2023), which suggests that this is a commonly accepted limitation within this stream of research.

Future research should therefore combine clickstream or user-level exposure data to trace actual information exposure paths and timing more precisely. In addition, although this study uses long-run data spanning 19 years to identify the broad determinants of vehicle purchase decisions, the importance of particular signals may vary across generation changes and changing market conditions. Future research should therefore examine more closely how attribute importance evolves across generations and model years.

Second, the scope of the sample and context is limited. This study analyzes monthly model-level sales of the gasoline Toyota RAV4 sold in the U.S. market. The gasoline RAV4 is representative in the sense that it was sold continuously over the sample period and accounted for a substantial share of total RAV4 sales. At the same time, however, this setting limits generalizability to other powertrains (e.g., hybrids and plug-in hybrids), competing models in the same segment (e.g., the Honda CR-V and Nissan Rogue), other national automobile markets, and product categories beyond automobiles. Future research should therefore extend the scope to multiple countries, vehicle models, and product categories to compare how the effects of online review signals vary across contexts.

Third, the scope of the online review data itself is limited. Although this study uses data from a major U.S. automobile review platform, consumer responses generated on other review platforms, social media, and video platforms could not be incorporated because of data availability constraints. In addition, over the 19-year observation period, the platform's user interface, review-sorting logic, and exposure structure may have changed to some extent, but these changes could not be systematically reflected in the analysis. Because such changes may alter the form and order of information that consumers actually encounter, future research should incorporate more diverse platform data together with information on interface changes.

Fourth, the potential endogeneity between online reviews and sales cannot be fully ruled out. This study uses a lag structure in which online review information accumulated up to the end of month $(t-1)$ is used to explain vehicle sales in month (t) , and it partially mitigates reverse causality and omitted-variable concerns by controlling for macroeconomic variables, search volume, COVID-19 shocks, and vehicle generation-change dummies. Nevertheless, the possibility remains that unobserved events or firm activities may have simultaneously influenced both online reviews and vehicle sales. For example, firm-side interventions such as advertising intensity or promotional activity may affect both sales and reviews, but these factors could not be controlled for because of data availability limitations. Future research should therefore secure richer control variables and more directly address endogeneity using methods such as the Gaussian copula-based control function approach (Park and Gupta, 2012).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eugene Lee: Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Formal analysis; Validation; Investigation; Data curation; Visualization; Writing – original draft; Project administration.

Sanbyul Im: Software; Validation; Investigation; Data curation.

Sang-uk Jung: Conceptualization; Methodology; Supervision; Writing – review and editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

We confirm that the authors do not have any conflict of interest.

Appendix

Appendix Table A1

Variable-Level Estimation Results for the Final Selected Model

Variable (Series code)	β (HAC se)	p_hac	LMG/Shapley %	VIF
const	18447.7385*** (928.5216)	0.00		
sentiment_latestN_unweighted_N25	978.4240* (573.8776)	0.09	1.28	1.91
D_review_shortage_recentN_N25	-1107.3199 (1493.3801)	0.46	0.30	
D_review_shortage_monthly_no_review	0.0000 (0.0000)		0.00	
Selling days	1306.3164*** (462.1812)	0.01	0.60	1.04
Chicago Fed National Activity Index (CFNAI)	-8.1817 (418.3345)	0.98	0.94	1.41
Google Trends "Toyota RAV4"	5491.2576*** (1301.0523)	0.00	22.43	9.68
Buying Conditions for Vehicles (U-Mich)	1682.4867 (1209.4555)	0.17	4.34	6.11
Retail Inventories/Sales Ratio: MV & Parts (MRTSIR441USN)	1807.3981*** (649.5195)	0.01	1.69	2.36
Motor Vehicle Retail Sales: Light Trucks (LTRUCKNSA)	5059.4554*** (970.8029)	0.00	16.81	6.24
CPI: New Vehicles (CUUR0000SETA01)	833.6826 (1463.0928)	0.57	8.86	7.87
10Y–3M Term Spread (T10Y3M/T10Y3MM)	647.6663 (713.3527)	0.37	6.64	2.71
Real Broad Dollar Index (RTWEXBGS)	2308.8122** (899.1197)	0.01	17.23	6.16
New Privately Owned Housing Units Authorized (PERMITNSA)	-712.2001 (722.7296)	0.33	7.79	4.15
Cash-for-Clunkers Dummy (2009.07–2009.08)	1175.6834 (1262.5126)	0.35	0.18	
FRED U.S. Recession Bars	-2129.4691 (2751.8960)	0.44	4.38	
2023 UAW strike (2023.09–2023.10)	4566.2894*** (1663.5942)	0.01	0.31	
Product launch dummy (2013.01–2013.03, 2018.12–2019.02)	-3876.8642*** (1279.6965)	0.00	0.36	
Month dummy: February	10593.8400*** (2355.9495)	0.00	0.55	
Month dummy: March	8867.3987*** (1343.0983)	0.00	0.60	
Month dummy: April	5382.1410*** (1198.0651)	0.00	0.30	
Month dummy: May	8646.6203*** (1358.4667)	0.00	0.57	
Month dummy: June	7673.4529*** (1139.5838)	0.00	0.26	
Month dummy: July	8391.9709*** (1382.9717)	0.00	0.55	
Month dummy: August	9579.6878*** (1730.6451)	0.00	0.94	
Month dummy: September	6427.5126*** (1548.3006)	0.00	0.21	
Month dummy: October	7216.9142*** (1008.2654)	0.00	0.28	
Month dummy: November	8864.9451*** (1257.2162)	0.00	0.39	
Month dummy: December	10092.5725*** (1251.1313)	0.00	1.22	

Note. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Values in parentheses are HAC-robust standard errors (Newey–West). The dependent variable is monthly Toyota RAV4 sales.

Note. Only continuous variables were standardized using z-scores; dummy variables were not standardized.

Note. The maximum variance inflation factor (max VIF) was calculated using only the continuous explanatory variables. Monthly dummies and policy/event dummies are reported separately and were not included in assessing whether the threshold was satisfied.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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